

CHEMICAL EXAMINATION OF THE ROOTS OF *ARISTOLOCHIA INDICA*, LINN. PART III. ISOLATION OF THE ALKALOID ARISTOLOCHINE.

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A brief summary of the reputed medicinal properties of the roots of *Aristolochia Indica* and of the chemical investigations on the principal members of the *Aristolochiaceæ* is included in Part I of this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 476). We have also indicated the occurrence of a crystalline alkaloid in *A. Indica* and proposed for it the name Aristolochine, which had been previously adopted by Pohl (*British Chem. Abs.*, 1892, I, 874) for the bitter toxic substances from *A. Rotunda* and *A. Clematitis*, and by Hesse (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1895, 233, 684) for an amorphous alkaloid from *A. Argentina*.

We are indebted to Prof. J. L. Simonsen for suggesting the search for this alkaloid and the principal difficulty has been that in the large majority of the samples of roots from different parts of South India, the alkaloidal content is only 0.05—0.07 per cent and is nil in some of the roots obtained locally. However, during the course of the regular analysis described in Part I, sufficient alkaloid was obtained in a pure condition to enable its characterisation.

Aristolochine crystallises from methyl alcohol and melts at 215°. It has the formula $C_{17}H_{19}O_3N$ and it is interesting to compare this with that of isearistolochic acid, $C_{17}H_{11}O_7N$, another constituent of the same roots. The base forms additive compounds with benzene and toluene, a property which is also exhibited by the cinchona alkaloids (Winterstein-Trier, "Die Alkaloide," 1931, p. 405).

We have now prepared a larger quantity of the alkaloid and are engaged in the investigation of its constitution.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Extraction and Isolation of the Alkaloid Aristolochine.—The crushed roots (50 kg.; alkaloidal content 0.05 %) were extracted with alcohol. The alcoholic extract was concentrated to a small bulk and treated with excess of

dilute hydrochloric acid, when a considerable amount of the extracted material separated as a thick viscous mass. The aqueous layer was separated, treated with excess of ammonia and repeatedly extracted with chloroform. The chloroform solution was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, filtered and extracted with dilute hydrochloric acid. The acid solution was concentrated on a water-bath, treated with animal charcoal, filtered and again concentrated in a vacuum desiccator over solid sodium hydroxide. The hydrochloride gradually separated as a microcrystalline powder (Fig. 2) and was purified by recrystallisation from water. This was dissolved in water and excess of ammonia added, when the base separated as a curdy precipitate. This was filtered and dried. It was found advisable to crystallise it first from toluene when the base was obtained in the form of an additive compound.

This addition compound dissolved readily in methyl alcohol, but the free base separated out soon as a crystalline powder, yield 20 g. When crystallised again from methyl alcohol (Fig. 1) it melted at 215° , $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -268.6^{\circ}$. [Found: C, 71.3, 71.4; H, 6.6, 6.6; N, 4.8, 4.9; M. W. (Kljatschkina *et al*, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1932, I, 1376) 289, 292; $C_{17}H_{19}O_3N$ requires C, 71.6; H, 6.7; N, 4.9 per cent. M.W., 285].

FIG. 1.

Aristolochine.

FIG. 2.

Aristolochine hydrochloride.

Properties of Aristolochine.—The hydrochloride melted at 268° (decomp.), $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -236.2^{\circ}$. (Found: Cl, 11.2. $C_{17}H_{19}O_3N$, HCl requires Cl, 11.0 per cent). The hydrobromide melted at 262° and decomposed at

282°. (Found : Br, 21.5. $C_{17}H_{19}O_3N$, HBr requires Br, 21.8 per cent). Both these salts are fairly soluble in water. The addition compound with toluene melted at 159° (decomp.) [Found : C, 74.4; H, 7.1; N, 4.2. $(C_{17}H_{19}O_3N)_2 \cdot C_7H_8$ requires C, 74.3; H, 7.0; N, 4.2 per cent], and that with benzene melted at 163° (decomp.). [Found : C, 74.2; H, 7.0; N, 4.4. $(C_{17}H_{19}O_3N)_2 \cdot C_6H_6$ requires C, 74.1; H, 6.8; N, 4.3 per cent]. From this also, the free base could be generated by treatment with methyl alcohol.

The *picrate* was prepared by adding the requisite amount of picric acid, dissolved in methyl alcohol to methyl alcoholic solution of the alkaloid. It gradually separated out on cooling, but could not be recrystallised from any solvent. It was repeatedly washed with boiling alcohol. The dried material decomposed at 222°. The picrolonate, m.p. 232° (decomp.), was also prepared in the same manner, and it was possible to crystallise it from methyl alcohol.

Aristolochine is sparingly soluble in most of the common solvents. It dissolves readily in alkalis, but is precipitated on saturating the solutions with carbon dioxide. It does not give any colouration with ferric chloride. It is found to contain one methoxy group [Found : OMe, 10.7. $C_{16}H_{16}O_2N$ -(OMe) requires OMe, 10.9 per cent], but no methylene-dioxy group (Hans Meyer, "Analyse und Konstitutionsermittlung organischen Verbindungen," 1931, p. 497; Sanchez and d'Alessio, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1932, II, 257). It is unacted upon by boiling alcoholic potash or reagents for carbonyl groups, and contains only one reactive hydrogen atom (Zerewitinoff estimation, Found : 1.2 H-atoms). The nitrogen atom is found to carry two methyl groups when estimated according to the method of Haberland and Slotta (*Ber.*, 1932, 65, 127) using Friedrich's micro-apparatus. (Found : NMe_2 , 15.7. $C_{15}H_{19}O_3NMe_2$ requires NMe_2 , 15.5 per cent).

The constitution of aristolochine as well as its pharmacological properties (the latter in the University Medical College, Mysore) are under investigation.

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